

Solution Stabilities of some Ternary Lanthanide Complexes with Picolinic Acid and the Tetrad-effect

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The occurrence of tetrad-effect in the solution stabilities of some ternary lanthanide complexes of the type $[\text{Ln}(\text{III})\text{A}.\text{pic}]$, where $\text{Ln}(\text{III})$ =tervalent lanthanide cation La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy or Er; A=NTA or EDTA; pic=picolinic acid, has been investigated. Solution stabilities have been determined in aqueous medium at 25° and ionic strength, $I=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3) by means of potentiometric pH-titrations using the Irving-Rossotti approach. The tetrad-effect has been explained with the help of the so called inclined-W hypothesis also.

THE coordination chemistry of lanthanides (Ln) has gained new dimensions by some recent investigations¹ on the solution stabilities of their dipicolinate and other chelates, wherein it has been stressed that the Ln(III) complexes can be successfully used as 'shift reagents' and 'structure probes'. The relevance of the occurrence of 'tetrad-effects'²⁻⁴ and the possibility of these complexes being isostructural over the entire Ln(III) series may lead to useful conclusions.

The present investigations were undertaken with the aim of studying the possible occurrence of tetrad-effects in the variations of solution stabilities of mixed ligand Ln(III) complexes with the number of 4f-electrons. The Ln(III).EDTA chelates have been found to be robust¹ and hence EDTA and also, for comparison, NTA have been chosen as primary ligands. The use of picolinic acid as secondary ligand may prove useful at a later stage when the possibility of these complexes being used as shift reagents or structure probes may also be examined.

Experimental

The Ln(III) nitrates (99.99% purity) were obtained from the Indian Rare Earths Ltd. Other chemicals (Merck G.R., AnalaR, Loba A.R.) were also of standard purity. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The Ln(III) solutions were standardised by complexometric titrations with EDTA and xylenol orange or bromopyrogallol red as indicator⁵. The metal and ligand solutions of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (final) concentration and a carbonate-free NaOH solution of 0.2 mol dm^{-3} concentration were used. The formation constants, $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$ and $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ were determined at 25° and ionic strength, $I=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3) by means of potentiometric pH-titrations using Irving-Rossotti approach⁶ and linear-plot method⁷. A Elico LI-120 digital

pH meter and a microburette (2 ml) were used for pH-titrations. The titrations were repeated for obtaining reproducible data. The experimental formation constant data were subjected to 'Q-test'⁸ for statistical refinement.

Results and Discussion

The formation constants, $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$, $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ and the $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}} - \log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}})$ values are presented in Table 1. The order, $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}} < \log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$ leads to negative values of $\Delta \log K$. The formation of complexes with NTA and EDTA may be represented as

The formation of MA complex in the first step involves combination of two oppositely charged species in both the cases (use of partly deprotonated species of NTA and EDTA in the first step of equations (1) and (2) also gives the same MA entities). This electrostatic attraction should cause rupture of hydration sphere of Ln(III) ion and desolvation of the acetate groups of NTA/EDTA. This should lead to a very favourable entropy factor. The complexes may, therefore, be regarded as mainly entropy stabilised⁹ particularly when the 4f-orbitals of Ln(III) ions are effectively shielded from ligand perturbations by the outerlying orbitals. The formation of MAL complex (in the second step) involves steric constraint and, particularly with EDTA, electrostatic repulsion. This explains why, in general, the $\Delta \log K$ values are more negative with EDTA. As a consequence of this electrostatic repulsion the stability sequence for the ternary complexes becomes (in general) $\text{NTA} > \text{EDTA}$, which is

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF 1:1 BINARY (ML) AND 1:1:1 TERNARY (MAL) COMPLEXES*

$I=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3), Temp. = 25°

Formation constant	Formation constant values for Ln(III) ions									
	La (4f ⁰)	Ce (4f ¹)	Pr (4f ²)	Nd (4f ³)	Sm (4f ⁵)	Eu (4f ⁶)	Gd (4f ⁷)	Tb (4f ⁸)	Dy (4f ⁹)	Er (4f ¹¹)
$\log K_{ML}^M$	4.04	4.16	4.27	4.36	4.56	4.82	4.64	4.88	4.91	5.02
A=NTA										
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	2.95	3.35	3.95	4.10	4.52	4.50	4.16	4.32	4.41	4.50
$-\Delta \log K$	1.09	0.81	0.32	0.26	0.04	0.32	0.48	0.56	0.50	0.52
A=EDTA										
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.60	3.65	3.84	4.00	4.48	4.12	4.06	4.22	4.35	4.40
$-\Delta \log K$	0.44	0.51	0.43	0.36	0.08	0.70	0.58	0.66	0.56	0.62

*M=Ln(III) ion; A=NTA or EDTA; L=picollinate (pic).

opposite of the known¹⁰ sequence EDTA>NTA for the MA complexes.

An increase in the formation constants with the standard entropies (Fig. 1) is an indication of the entropy stabilisation of these complexes. The plots are in two segments with a depression at Gd^{III} (4f⁷-configuration), which demonstrates the occurrence of tetrad-effect. The values of formation constants when plotted against the number of 4f-electrons yield plots (Fig. 2) having a marked dip at Gd^{III} due to tetrad-effect. The occurrence of an expected minor break at the 4f⁹-4f⁴ stage is not seen very clearly. It has not been possible to examine the

possibility of occurrence of the third (minor) break at the 4f¹⁰-4f¹¹ stage due to non-availability of higher lanthanides.

Fig. 1. Variation in formation constant values with the standard entropies, S_M^0 ($\text{cal K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of the Ln elements: (A) $\log K_{ML}^M$, (B) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (A=NTA) and (C) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (A=EDTA).

Fig. 2. Variation in formation constant values with the number of 4f-electrons of the Ln(III) ions: (A) $\log K_{ML}^M$, (B) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (A=NTA) and (C) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (A=EDTA).

There is a lack of agreement on the explanation of the phenomenon of tetrad-effect. Three major attempts have been made in this regard which seek to attribute the occurrence of the tetrad-effects to (i) change in coordination number^{11,12} of Ln(III) ion at Gd^{III}, (ii) change in hydration number^{13,15} of Ln(III) ion at Gd^{III} and (iii) change in total orbital angular momentum of Ln elements, i.e. the so-called 'inclined-W hypothesis'⁴ (Fig. 3). Recently, it has been suggested¹ that perhaps a statistical mechanical

explanation may be required to offer a comprehensive explanation for these breaks.

second segment can not be linear as claimed by Sinha⁴.

Fig. 3. Variation in formation constant values with the total orbital angular momentum, L_{Ln} of the Ln-elements (inclined-W plot). The fourth segment of inclined-W has been drawn as dotted line (which may not be its actual shape) as we have not been able to study the Ln(III) elements beyond $4f^{11}$ configuration (Er^{III}).

It may be noticed that the inclined-W (Fig. 3) is not symmetrical and the segments (particularly the second segment) are not linear. Similar deviations from symmetry and linearity have been reported earlier¹⁶. In all those cases where a dip at Gd^{III} occurs as a manifestation of tetrad-effects, the

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